

Kinetics of Silver-Catalysed Oxidation of Ethylene Glycol by Peroxydisulphate Ion—Part I.

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The kinetics of silver-catalysed oxidation of ethylene glycol by peroxydisulphate ion in aqueous medium has been studied. The reaction is found to be first order w.r.t. $S_2O_8^{2-}$ ion and zero order w.r.t. glycol. However, the rate constant is found to decrease with an increase either in the concentration of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ or that of glycol. The first order rate constant also decreases with time in any particular run. The mole ratio for the reaction is 4 moles of $S_2O_8^{2-}$: 1 mole of glycol. The effect of ionic strength has been investigated by using K_2SO_4 as the neutral salt. The salt effect has been found to be negative and of the primary exponential type in the region of low ionic strength. K^+ , Na^+ , H^+ , Zn^{++} and Mg^{++} ions have been found to have specific inhibitory effect, it being in the order of $K^+ > Na^+ > Mg^{++} > H^+ > Zn^{++}$. The energy of activation, frequency factor and entropy of activation values are: -13790 cal.mole $^{-1}$, 5.445×10^5 litre mole $^{-1}$.sec $^{-1}$ and -32.33 E.U. respectively.

Peroxydisulphate ion is a powerful oxidising agent, its oxidation potential being nearly -2.01 volts. However, the oxidation reactions involving this ion are slow and have been studied kinetically. Due to comparatively milder oxidising power the kinetics of oxidation of various organic substrates by $S_2O_8^{2-}$ have been studied previously by many workers as reviewed by House¹. These oxidation processes in many cases present many complicating features, e.g., the oxidation of oxalic acid and oxalate ion² and the oxidation of alcohols³. A review of the literature shows that no systematic kinetic study of the oxidation of polyhydric alcohols by $S_2O_8^{2-}$ has so far been made. Further, in previous kinetic studies no attempt seems to have been made to isolate and identify the various reaction products to substantiate the reaction mechanism suggested. Besides this in all previous studies, the simultaneous self-decomposition of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ has been ignored which, in our opinion, is not sound. Hence a systematic kinetic study of the oxidation of different polyhydric alcohols by $S_2O_8^{2-}$ is proposed with particular emphasis on the isolation and identification of different reaction products and attempt to study the kinetics of different intermediate stages, wherever possible.

The present paper deals with our preliminary observations on the kinetic study of the silver-catalysed oxidation of ethylene glycol by $S_2O_8^{2-}$. It may be mentioned here that Mishra and Ghosh⁴ have recently studied some aspects of this reaction and their results are in general agreement with ours.

1. D. A. House, *Chem. Rev.*, 1962, **62**, 185.
2. T. L. Allen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 3589; *ibid.*, 1961, **83**, 4352; S. P. Srivastava and S. Ghosh, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1953, **202**, 191; *ibid.*, 1956, **205**, 332; Y. K. Gupta and S. Ghosh, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. (India)*, 1958, **27A**, 258; *J. Inorg. and Nucl. Chem.*, 1959, **11**, 320.
3. D. L. Ball, M. M. Crutchfield and J. O. Edward, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 1599; L. S. Levitt and E. R. Malinowski, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 4517; *ibid.*, 1958, **80**, 5334; K. B. Wilberg, *ibid.*, 1959, **81**, 252.
4. D. D. Mishra and S. Ghosh, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, (India), 1964, **34A**, 317.

EXPERIMENTAL

$K_2S_2O_8$ of G.R., E. Merck quality, silver nitrate of Analar, B.D.H. quality and ethylene glycol, of L.R., B.D.H. quality after redistillation were used. All other chemicals used were also of Analar grade. The solutions were prepared by direct weighing and dissolving in redistilled water from a Corning distilling still. A freshly prepared solution of $K_2S_2O_8$ was always used.

All reactions were carried out in Pyrex bottles, coated with black-Japan. Measured quantities of the solutions of $K_2S_2O_8$ (or ethylene glycol) and silver nitrate were kept in a thermostat maintained at the temp. of experiments (35°), with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The reaction was started by running in the required volume of ethylene glycol (or $K_2S_2O_8$) solution into the reaction vessel. The progress of the reaction was studied by estimating the unreacted $S_2O_8^{2-}$ iodometrically by the method of Szabo⁵, as modified by Khulbe and Srivastava⁶.

Effect of Peroxydisulphate concentration: The results obtained at different initial concentrations of $K_2S_2O_8$ on the oxidation of glycol have been summarised in the following table. k_1 (unimol) gives the first order rate constant for total reaction while k_2 (unimol.) is the first order rate constant for catalytic decomposition of $K_2S_2O_8$ alone. It may be pointed out that in any run the 1st order constant (k_1) decreases with time, hence in this and other subsequent tables, k_1 has been evaluated graphically from the initial rate.

TABLE I

Ethylene glycol = 2% = 0.3225M approx., Temp. = 35° $AgNO_3$ = 0.001M

Initial concentration	k_1 (unimol)	k_2 (unimol)	$k = k_1 - k_2$
of $K_2S_2O_8$	$\times 10^3$	$\times 10^3$	$\times 10^3$
0.005M	8.24	1.57	6.67
0.010M	7.55	1.55	6.00
0.015M	7.44	1.47	5.97
0.020M	7.13	1.40	5.73
0.025M	5.84	1.37	4.37

As the concentration of $K_2S_2O_8$ is increased, the value of the first order rate constant decreases (c.f. the effect of $K_2S_2O_8$ on the oxidation of alcohols⁷). This may be due to the increase in the ionic strength or due to the specific inhibitory effect of K^+ ion or both.

Effect of Ethylene glycol concentration: Table II embodies the results which show the effect of different initial concentrations of ethylene glycol on the reaction rate.

5. Csanyi Szabo and Z. Galiba, *Anal. Chem.*, 1952, **135**, 269.

6. K. C. Khulbe and S. P. Srivastava, *Agra. Uni. J. Reserach (Sc)*, 1960, IX, Pt. II, 177.

7. K. C. Khulbe and S. P. Srivastava, *Agra. Uni. J. Research (Sc.)*, 1965, XIV, Pt. III, 125.

TABLE II

K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ = 0.01M		AgNO ₃ = 0.001M.		Temp. = 35°
Initial conc. of ethylene glycol	k ₁ (unimol) × 10 ³	k ₂ (unimol) × 10 ³	k (= k ₁ - k ₂) × 10 ³	
1%	8.41	1.55	6.86	
2%	7.55	1.55	6.00	
3%	7.24	1.55	5.69	
4%	6.78	1.55	5.23	
5%	5.94	1.55	4.39	
6%	5.48	1.55	3.93	
7%	5.08	1.55	3.53	

It is seen that the first order rate constant decreases with the increase in the concentration of ethylene glycol. This suggests that ethylene glycol, in spite of using freshly distilled sample, may have some traces of impurities which may be exercising an inhibiting action on the oxidation of ethylene glycol by S₂O₈²⁻.

Effect of temperature : The reaction was studied at five different temperatures from 25° to 45° to calculate the frequency factor, energy of activation and entropy of activation, which are given in the following table.

TABLE III

Temp.	Ethylene glycol = 2%		K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ = 0.01M		AgNO ₃ = 0.001M	
	k ₁ (unimol) × 10 ³	k ₂ (unimol) × 10 ³	k = k ₁ - k ₂ × 10 ³	A × 10 ⁻⁵ (lit.mole ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹)	E (calmole ⁻¹)	ΔS (E.U.)
25°	3.16	0.71	2.45	5.140		-32.36
30°	4.90	1.03	3.87	5.618	15030	-32.23
35°	7.08	1.49	5.59	5.575	12930	-32.29
40°	10.00	2.30	7.70	5.387	13400	-32.39
45°	14.37	3.20	11.17	5.505		-32.38
			Mean :	5.445	13790	-32.33

The average value of the frequency factor for this reaction (viz., 5.445×10^5 lit. mole⁻¹ sec.⁻¹) is of the same order as reported by Khulbe and Srivastava (*loc. cit.*) for the oxidation of isopropyl alcohol. (9.334×10^5).

The mean value of energy of activation comes out to be 13790 cal.mole⁻¹, while that calculated graphically is 13650 cal.mole⁻¹. It may be mentioned here that a large variation in the energy of activation with temperature has been reported by Mishra and Ghosh (*loc. cit.*) for this reaction, for which no plausible reason could be assigned by them.

This large variation observed by Mishra and Ghosh may be due to insufficient care taken to purify the reacting materials. It may be mentioned here that the energy of activation and entropy of activation found by us for this reaction are of similar magnitude as reported by Khulbe and Srivastava (*loc. cit.*) for the oxidation of isopropyl alcohol. This suggests that the essential mechanism of these oxidation processes is probably similar.

The rate constant for this reaction can, therefore, be expressed as:—

$$k = 5.445 \times 10^5 e^{-13790/RT}$$

Effect of Ionic Strength of the medium: The effect of ionic strength on the oxidation of ethylene glycol by $S_2O_8^{2-}$ was studied by adding different amounts of K_2SO_4 to the reaction mixture which contained fixed concentrations of ethylene glycol, $K_2S_2O_8$ and the catalyst. The results of these measurements are summarised in the following table:

TABLE IV

K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ = 0.01M glycol = 1% AgNO ₃ = 0.001M Temp. = 35°				
Concentration of added K ₂ SO ₄	μ	μ [‡]	k (unimol) × 10 ³	log k
—	0.031	.1760	6.860	−2.164
0.005M	0.046	.2144	6.667	−2.176
0.010M	0.061	.2469	6.265	−2.203
0.015M	0.076	.2756	5.757	−2.239
0.020M	0.091	.3016	5.378	−2.269
0.025M	0.106	.3255	5.171	−2.286
0.030M	0.121	.3479	4.894	−2.310
0.040M	0.151	.3885	4.491	−2.347
0.050M	0.181	.4254	3.950	−2.403
0.060M	0.211	.4593	3.846	−2.415
0.080M	0.271	.5205	3.543	−2.450
0.100M	0.331	.5753	3.362	−2.473

On plotting $(\mu)^{\ddagger}$ against $\log k$ (Fig. 1), we find a linear curve in the region of low ionic strength; however this linear relationship is not maintained when the ionic strength is about

FIGURE 1 EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION OF GLYCOL BY $S_2O_8^{2-}$

Fig. 1

0.2 or more. It follows from the above observations that the negative effect of ionic strength obtained is of the primary exponential type in the region of low ionic strength. However, in any particular run, the decrease in the 1st order rate constant with time is more pronounced with an increase in ionic strength (vide Table V) for which no plausible explanation is forthcoming.

TABLE V

Ethylene Glycol = 2% $K_2S_2O_8 = 0.01M$ $AgNO_3 = 0.001M$. Temp. = 35°

Salt added	Concn. (M)	μ	k (unimol) for total reaction with time (min.)					
			10	25	45	75	135	200
No salt	—	0.031	7.23	6.98	6.86	6.79	6.46	6.27
Na_2SO_4	0.10	0.331	6.25	5.71	4.83	4.71	3.66	3.45
„	0.25	0.781	6.16	5.67	5.10	4.20	3.46	3.25
K_2SO_4	0.10	0.331	6.26	5.24	4.71	4.03	3.59	3.43
„	0.25	0.781	6.20	5.87	4.57	3.52	3.18	3.00

Effect of Specific Ions : In order to study the effect of specific ions, various cations were employed at constant ionic strength. The results obtained are tabulated below :

TABLE VI

$K_2S_2O_8 = 0.01M$ Glycol = 1% $AgNO_3 = 0.001M$ Temp. = 35° $\mu = 0.181$

Cations added	Concn. (M)	k_1 (unimol) $\times 10^3$	k_2 (unimol) $\times 10^3$	$k (= k_1 - k_2)$ $\times 10^3$
—	—	8.41	1.55	6.86
K_2SO_4	0.05	4.97	1.02	3.95
Na_2SO_4	0.05	5.32	0.97	4.35
H_2SO_4	0.05	5.87	1.17	4.70
$MgSO_4$	0.0375	5.66	1.09	4.57
$ZnSO_4$	0.0375	6.38	1.08	5.30

The above results show that, besides general salt effect, ions have their own specific effect on the reaction rate. It may also be concluded from the above observations that, with the exception of H^+ , probably monovalent ions have greater negative specific ionic effect on the reaction rate than divalent ones.

Mole Ratio : The mole ratio between $S_2O_8^{2-}$ and glycol was determined after taking into account the self-decomposition of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ in presence of the catalyst. This comes out roughly four moles of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ to one mole of glycol.

Further work to isolate and identify the reaction products and to work out the different intermediate stages is in progress.

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